

**New species of *Agapanthia danilevskyi* from South Kazakhstan
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: A new species *Agapanthia danilevskyi* sp. n. is described from South Kazakhstan. It is similar to *A. villosoviridescens* (DeGeer, 1775), but elytra without erect setae.

***Agapanthia danilevskyi* sp. n.**
(Fig 1)

Type locality. South Kazakhstan, left bank of Syrdarya River, about 41°16'N, 67°54'E, 260m.

Diagnosis. Only one male available; body moderately elongated; head with yellow pubescence, with very dense brush between antennae; genae about as long as lower eye lobe; eyes slightly convex, nearly flat, with deep emargination; antennae very thin, black, without setae tufts, reaching beyond elytral apices by 5 joints; 3rd antennal joint slightly lightened basally; 1st and 2nd joints with black pubescence; three basal fourth of 3rd joint covered with white recumbent pubescence, apical fourth with black pubescence; whole length of 3rd joint with long suberect setae concentrated apically; others joints covered with white pubescence to about half; the length of antennal joints: 1st - 3.3 mm, 2nd - 0,4 mm, 3rd - 4.0 mm, 4th - 2.5 mm, 5th - 2.0 mm, 6th - 1.6 mm, 7th - 1.5 mm; 8th - 1.4 mm, 9th - 1.4mm, 10th - 1.3 mm, 11th - 1.4 mm, 12th - 1.3 mm; prothorax transverse, its basal width 2.9mm, distal - 2.6mm, at middle - 3.0 mm; its length - 2.6 mm; pronotum with very dense, wide central and lateral yellow setae stripes, looks black in between, with several moderately long suberect black setae, without erect setae; pronotal punctation regular, very dense, but not conjugated; scutellum transversely-oval with dense yellow pubescence; elytra about 2.8 times longer than wide, parallelsided; with dense contrast small

M.A. Lazarev

yellow patches and nearly glabrous in between; with numerous adpressed black setae, but without erect setae; elytral apices slightly sharpened; elytral punctuation very dense, partly transversally conjugated; larger than pronotal punctuation; legs black, with very dense yellow (partly white-grayish) pubescence; ventral side of the body with very dense yellow and white-grayish pubescence, abdomen segments with numerous glabrous dots; body length: 15,4 mm, width: 4.0 mm.

Another sympatric desert *Agapanthia* – *A. auliensis* Pic, 1907 of similar size has red antennae, elytra covered with long black erect setae and with wide humeral grey stripes. Similar *A. villosovirdescence* is distributed very far northwards and can be easily distinguished from *A. danilevskyi* **sp. n.** by the presence of erect elytral setae.

Distribution. Kazakhstan: left bank of Syrdarya River just opposite Chardara, about 41°16'N, 67°54'E, 260m.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, South Kazakhstan, left bank of Syrdarya River opposite Chardara, about 41°16'N, 67°54'E, 260m, 22.4.1980, G.Nikolaev - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia).

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Fig 1. *Agapanthia danilevskyi* sp. n.: holotype, male.

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